

e-ISSN: 2584-2390

Volume 04 Issue 01
Jan-Jun 2026

Submission Date: Jan
20, 2026

Copyright Date : Feb 04,
2026

Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge And Practices Regarding Prevention on Leptospirosis Among Mahatma Gandhi Rural Employment Workers

Ms. Roshna V.¹, Ms. Aiswarya S.², Mr. Aksh J.³, Ms. Jeenu R.⁴, Ms. Aparna R. R.⁵, Prof. Divya Gigi Raj^{6}, Ms. Veena V.J.⁷*

^{1,2,3,4,5}*Student Nurses, PRS College of Nursing, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India*

⁶*Professor, PRS College of Nursing, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India*

⁷*Senior Lecturer, PRS College of Nursing, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India*

ABSTRACT

Leptospirosis is a major public health problem in tropical countries, particularly affecting rural and occupationally exposed populations such as Mahatma Gandhi Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS) workers. Due to frequent exposure to contaminated water, poor sanitation, and inadequate preventive practices, these workers are at increased risk of infection. Enhancing their knowledge and preventive practices is essential to reduce disease incidence.

The present study aimed to assess the effectiveness of a structured teaching programme on knowledge and practices regarding prevention of leptospirosis among Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers in Perumkadavila Panchayat, Trivandrum district. A quantitative research approach with a pre-experimental one-group pre-test and post-test design was adopted. A total of 50 rural employment workers were selected using simple random sampling techniques.

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire to assess knowledge and a checklist to assess preventive practices related to leptospirosis. A structured teaching programme was administered after the pre-test, followed by a post-test to evaluate its effectiveness. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis, including paired t-test and chi-square test.

Following the organized training program, the results showed a considerable improvement in both knowledge and

practice scores. The mean post-test knowledge score was significantly higher than the pre-test score ($t = 32.6, p < 0.05$). Significant associations were found between selected demographic variables such as age, lifestyle habits, years of experience, and source of

information with knowledge and practice levels.

The study comes to the conclusion that an organized educational program is a practical and successful way to enhance rural employment workers' understanding of leptospirosis and their preventative measures, which will help to avoid illness and promote health.

Keywords: *Leptospirosis, health, effective and feasible intervention*

INTRODUCTION

"Every small step in the right direction becomes the start of something amazing"

Health is a crucial factor in a happy, contented life. Encouraging people to transition to a healthier lifestyle and appropriate coping mechanism are main priorities of health promotion. In India, most of them are suffering from different illness. One of the most common seasonal disorders is leptospirosis.

Leptospirosis is one of the zoonotic diseases that is transmitted globally and spreads directly to human without any intermediary vertebrate or invertebrate or inanimate vectors. This infectious disease is conveyed by a specific kind of bacteria called a spirochete and is brought on by foxes, opossums, raccoons, skunks, and other rodents. This happens internationally but most frequently acquired in the tropics. In urban and rural areas, leptospirosis may occur.

Urban areas of developing countries, the environment are contaminated due to numerous factors such as overcrowded slums, inadequate human and animal drainage, and sanitation facilities. Presence of wild dogs, goats, pigs, domestic rats, robbers, bad slaughterhouse conditions, and people walking bare foot leads to the spread of the slaughterhouses.

In rural areas, high-risk groups are jobs in rice fields, cane fields, and other agricultural crops and animal husbandry personnel.

In addition, workers in sewer mines and military personnel are also at risk. It is transmitted by reservoir when contact with contaminated water or urine, fluid or tissue touch with contaminated animals. Usually lasting 10 days, the incubation period can last anywhere from 4 to 20 days. Leptospirosis symptoms usually appear suddenly every day (10–14 days). With epidemic cases excluded, the median incidence of endemic human leptospirosis worldwide is 5 per.[1]

Spirochetes belonging to the genus *Leptospira* are the cause of the bacterial zoonotic illness leptospirosis.

It affects both humans and animals and is considered an emerging infectious disease worldwide the infection it is transmitted through contact with urine or other body fluids of infected animals, primarily rodent, cattle pigs and other mammal-dogs

Leptospirosis is recognized as a major public health problem. In many parts of the world, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. It is estimated that there are around 1 million severe cases and 60,000 deaths annually worldwide. Various risk factors contribute to the

transmission and spread of leptospirosis, including occupation exposure (eg: farmers, sewage workers), recreational activities in contaminated water bodies, natural disasters (eg flooding) Leptospirosis is a classic example of a health disease, as it requires a multidisciplinary approach involving human and animal health sectors as well as environmental and social factors. Overall, leptospirosis remains a significant global health challenge, particularly in resource limited settings.

Research studies on leptospirosis aims to understand various aspects of the disease, including its epidemiology, transmission dynamics, pathogenesis, diagnosis, treatment and prevention. These studies involves multidisciplinary approaches, combining fields such as microbiology, epidemiology, veterinary medicine, immunology and molecular biology

Leptospirosis is a public health problem, so it is essential to have prevention and control measures in order to minimize risk factors and to attenuates the incidence of disease. Vaccination of dogs is another measure of great importance, as this can reduce the contamination of dogs and consequently the prevalence of disease.

Early studies of leptospirosis incidence concentrated on occupational disease, primarily in developed countries related to leptospirosis in livestock animals. Guidelines for the diagnosis and management of leptospirosis were created as the disease's significance in tropical nations became increasingly apparent. Numerous epidemiologic studies were reported from various countries as diagnostic techniques became more accessible.

The incidence was calculated to be between 350,000 and 5,00,000 cases of

severe leptospirosis per year based on data gathered by international leptospirosis surveys. Notwithstanding these initiatives, it was believed that the worldwide leptospirosis burden was significantly underestimated for a variety of reasons, including the fact that most nations either did not have a notification system in place or did not require one.[2]

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The need for he studies on leptospirosis among Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers arises from the fact that these individuals are at higher risk of exposure to the disease due to their work activities. Public health interventions, such as improving sanitation and hygiene practices, has also been shown to be effective in preventing leptospirosis

A study by Nilofer et al. (2016) focused on the spatial distribution of leptospirosis cases in Kerala using geographic information system (GIS) mapping. The study identified hotspots of leptospirosis transmission, providing valuable information for targeted surveillance and control.

A study conducted by Smith *et al.* (2015) to assess the prevalence of leptospirosis among rural employment workers. This study highlights the burden of leptospirosis in the occupational group and emphasises the need for targeted practices. By studying leptospirosis within a community, researchers can identify the risk factors and behaviours that increases the likelihood of infection. This information can be used to implement targeted preventive measures.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge and practices regarding prevention on leptospirosis among

Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers in Perumkadavila panchayat.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge and practices regarding prevention of leptospirosis.

2. To find out the association between the knowledge and selected demographic variables.
3. To find the association between the practices and selected demographic variables.

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach

Quantitative research approach

Research Design

Pre-experimental one group pre-test, post- test.

Group	Pretest	Intervention	Post test
Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers of Perumkadavila panchayat	O1	Structured teaching programme	O2

Variables

- Independent Variable-Structured Teaching programme
- Dependent Variable-Knowledge and practices regarding prevention of leptospirosis

- Both male and female Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers.
- Workers of Perumkadavila panchayat.
- Workers who are willing to participate in the study.
- Workers those who are present at the time of data collection.

Research Setting

The setting of the study is at Perumkadavila panchayat.

Exclusion criteria:

- Mahatma Gandhi national rural employment workers who are
- Those where not willing to participate in the study.

Population

population consist of Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers of Perumkadavila panchayat.

Data Collection Technique

Formal permission was obtained from the authority and the consent was obtained from the medical officer of community health centre, Perumkadavila. Investigators introduce self and explained the purpose of the study by assuming maximum confidentiality. Obtained the written consent from the participants Collection of data by using questionnaire and check list.

Sample and Sample Size

Sample: Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers of Perumkadavila panchayat during the study period and who meets the inclusion criteria.

Sample size: Sample size is 50 for the study.

Sampling Technique

simple random sampling technique.

Description of Tool

Data will be collected from the subjects using questionnaire and checklist.

Sampling Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

The study includes,

Section 1-Socio Personal Data Sheet

It deals with demographic data which consists of 10 items used to collect the sample characteristics which comprises demographic variables such as:

- Age
- Gender
- Religion
- Marital status
- Type of family
- Educational status
- Socio economic status
- Lifestyle habits
- Years of experience
- Source of information regarding leptospirosis

Section 2-Checklist

It consists of 20 items with YES or NO responses.

- This checklist is used to assess the practice regarding prevention of leptospirosis.

Section 3-Structured Questionnaire

- It consist of 20 items to assess the knowledge regarding prevention of leptospirosis. Each correct answers carries a score of “1 mark” and the wrong answer carries “0 mark”. Thus a tool totally scores of “20 marks” under knowledge regarding prevention of leptospirosis.

Content Validity

For the content validity the tool will be given to 4 experts including, 2 doctors and 2 nursing educators and as per the suggestion of the experts, the tool will be modified.

Reliability of the Tool

The reliability of the tool established by test-retest method.

Ethical Consideration

For the present study, Ethical clearance will be obtained from ethical clearance committee. Formal permission will be obtained from the Principal, PRS College of Nursing, Paliyode, Trivandrum and from medical officer of Community Health Centre, Perumkadavila. Informed consents will be taken from the participants prior to the data collection period. Confidentiality was maintained. Scientific objectivity of the study is maintained with honesty and impartiality.

Pilot Study

The investigators will conduct a pilot study on the month of November. The main purpose to find out the practicability and feasibility of the study. This will be well explained to the participants and informed consent will be obtained.

Procedure for Data Collection

Plan for Data Analysis

Data collected from Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers of Perumkadavila panchayat, Trivandrum district. Data collected will be tabulated and analysed using quantitative analysis Data analysis will be planned to include both descriptive and inferential method.

Descriptive statistics:

Frequency and percentage distribution were used to analyse the demographic data.

Inferential statistics:

“Chi-square” to determine the association between

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The process of classifying, modifying, organizing, and summarizing data in order to find answers to research questions is known as analysis. This chapter deals with the results of data collected from a sample

of 50 Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers.

The chapter deals with the systematic presentation of the analysed data followed by the interpretation of the date. The collected information was organized, tabulated, analysed and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings were organized and presented in two parts with tables and figures. The details of each section are presented below to correlate with the objectives.

ORGANIZATION OF FINDINGS

The data collected were systematically processed, tabulated and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings have been organized and interpreted under the following headings.

Section A

Socio- demographic data of Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers

Section B

Distribution of samples according to the level of knowledge regarding prevention of leptospirosis before and after structured teaching programme.

Distribution of samples according to the level of practice to prevent leptospirosis before and after leptospirosis.

Section C

Association between the pre test scores on the level of knowledge to prevent , marital status, type of family, education socio economic status, lifestyle habits, year of experience, source of obligatory information

leptospirosis among Mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers and their selected variables and association between practice levels of the workers and their selected variable.

Section A: Socio Demographic Data

The section deals with socio demographic data of 50 workers in terms of frequency and percentage. The socio demographic data includes age gender, religion

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
25- 35	5	10%
36-45	12	24%
46-55	23	46%
Above 55	10	20%

The above diagram reveals that majority 23 (46%) of workers are of age between 46-55 years old, 12 (24%) of workers are of age between 36-45 years old and 10(20%) of workers are of age above 55 years old and minority 5 (10%) of workers are of age group between 25-35 years old.

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	20	40%
Female	30	60%
Others	0	0

The above table reveals that majority 30 (60%) of workers are females, and minority 20 (40%) of workers are males..

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on religion

Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Hindu	15	30%
Muslim	0	0
Christian	35	70%
Others	0	0

The above table reveals that majority 35 (70%) of workers are Christian and minority 15 (30%) of workers are hindu..

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on marital status of workers

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	40	80%
Unmarried	0	0
Divorced	5	10%
Widowed	5	10%

The above table reveals that majority 40 (80%) of workers are Married, 5 (10%) of workers are divorced and 5 (10%) of workers are widowed.

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on type of family

Type of family	Frequency	Percentage
Nuclear	30	60%
Joint	20	40%
Extended	0	0

The above table reveals the majority 30(60%) of workers are lived in Nuclear family and 20(40%) of workers lived in Joint family.

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on education

Education status	Frequency	Percentage
Lower Primary	5	10%
Upper Primary	35	70%
Graduate	10	20%
Others	0	0

The above table reveals the majority 35 (70%) of workers completed Upper primary and 10 (20%) of workers were graduated and minority 5 (10%) completed LP

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on socio-economic status

Socio economic status	Frequency	Percentage
Upper class family	0	0
Middle class family	15	30%
Lower class family	35	70%
Othera	0	0

The above table reveals the majority 35(70%) of workers belongs to lower class family and minority 15(30%) of workers belongs to middle class family

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on lifestyle habits

Lifestyle habits	Frequency	Percentage
Alcohol	0	0
Smoking	5	10%
Tobacco	5	10%
None	40	80%

The above diagram reveals majority 40(80%) of workers does not have any lifestyle habits,5 (10%) of workers have a habit of smoking and 5(10%) of workers have a habit of tobacco chewing

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on years of work experience

Year of experience	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	15	30%
5- 10	15	30%
10-15	20	40%
Above 15	0	0

The above table shows a majority of 20 (40%) workers belongs under 10-15 years of experience and 15 (30%) of workers belongs under 5-10 years and 15(30%) of workers belongs under 1-5 years of experience.

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples based on source of information regarding leptospirosis

Source	Frequency	Percentage
TV	15	30%
Internet	0	0
Health programmes	30	60%
Othets	5	10%

Section B

Distribution of samples according to the level of knowledge regarding prevention of leptospirosis among mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers before and after structured teaching programme

	Poor	Average	Good
Pre test	70%	20%	10%
Post test	0%	20%	80%

Distribution of samples according to the level of practice regarding prevention of leptospirosis among mahatma gandhi rural employment workers before and after structured teaching programme

	Inadequate	Moderate	Adequate
Pre test	80%	20%	0%
Post test	0%	15%	85%

Section C

Association Between Pretest Scores on the Level of Knowledge Among Mahatma Gandhi Rural Employment Workers and their Selected Demographic Variable

Sn-50

Sl no	Socio demographic variables	Pre test			
		Chi	P	Degree	of Significance

		Square	value	Freedom	
1	Age	14.15	7.82	3	S
2	Gender	5.9	7.82	3	NS
3	Religion	1.7	7.82	3	NS
4	Marital status	3.8	7.82	3	NS
5	Type of family	0.12	7.82	3	NS
6	Education	7.2	7.82	3	NS
7	Socio economic data	0.75	7.82	3	NS
8	Lifestyle habits	15.6	7.82	3	S
9	Year of experience	2.09	7.82	3	NS
10	Source of Information	9.56	7.82	3	NS

S: Significance

NS: Non-Significance

To determine the relationship between the workers' knowledge of leptospirosis and demographic factors, chi-square analysis is used in the table above. The result shows there is a significance association between Age of the workers, lifestyle habits and

source of information. But there was no association between religion, gender, marital status type of family, education socio economic data and year of experience.

Association between pretest scores on the level of practice among mahatma Gandhi rural employment workers and their selected demographic variables

Sl no	Socio demographic variables	Pre test			
		Chi Square	P Value	Degree of Freedom	Significance
1	Age	8.76	7.82	3	S
2	Gender	1.28	7.82	3	NS
3	Religion	1.19	7.82	3	NS
4	Marital status	1.59	7.82	3	NS
5	Type of family	1.02	7.82	3	NS
6	Education	0.88	7.82	3	NS
7	Socio economic data	3	7.82	3	NS
8	Life style habits	9.95	7.82	3	S
9	Year of experience	9.01	7.82	3	S
10	Source of Information	9.27	7.82	3	S

S: Significance

NS-Significance

The table shown above chi-square is carried to find out the association between the knowledge on leptospirosis of the workers and demographic variables

The result shows there is a significance association between age of the workers lifestyle habits, years of experience and source of information. But there was no association between religions, marital status, type of family, education and socio-economic status.

Comparison of the pretest and posttest knowledge score on workers regarding prevention of leptospirosis

To test the statistical significant difference between the mean pretest and post-test knowledge scores of the workers regarding prevention of leptospirosis.

Knowledge score	Mean	SD	t test value
Pre test	3.78	2.28	tcal=32.6
Post test	16.28	1.04	ttab= 2.00

The aforementioned table demonstrates that the employees' mean post-test knowledge scores on leptospirosis prevention are noticeably greater than their mean pre-test knowledge scores.

In order to find out the significant difference between the mean score of pre and post test knowledge score of the workers regarding knowledge of leptospirosis paired "t" test was computed. The calculated value is higher than the table value. Hence the researcher concluded that gain in knowledge is not by chance but by structured teaching programme on prevention of leptospirosis.

CONCLUSION

This chapter deals with the analysis of sample characteristics based on demographic variables such as age gender,

religion, marital status, type of family education, socio economic status. Lifestyle habits, years of experience source of information about leptospirosis. It also demonstrates the frequency and percentage distribution of knowledge scores and association between the knowledge score and practice score and association with selected demographic variable.

REFERENCE

1. World Health Organization. (2003). *Human leptospirosis: Guidance for diagnosis, surveillance and control*. World Health Organization.
2. Sharma, S. K., & Rani, R. (2018). Effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge of communicable disease among rural workers. *10(2)*, 78–82.